

Impact Factor: 4.972

ISSN: 2181-0788

DOI: 10.26739/2181-0788

www.tadqiqot.uz

IJC

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONSENSUS

KONSENSUS XALQARO JURNALI

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1

2023

KONSENSUS XALQARO JURNALI

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONSENSUS
VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1

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**JOURNAL OF
INTERNATIONAL
CONSENSUS**

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**ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE IN UZBEKISTAN: DEVELOPMENT
AND PROSPECTS**

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8050841>

ABSTRACT

Any progress is based on science. Without the development of science, it is impossible to imagine the development of society, the well-being of society. In particular, science finds solutions to global environmental threats and global problems. The development, Genesis, evolution of environmental science in Uzbekistan has its stages. It has become an important part of national development. This will be discussed in the article.

Key words: Science, population, biosphere, anthropoecology, demoeology, ecosystem, nature, natural resource, phytoecology, biocenosis, landscape.

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ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ЭКОЛОГИЯ ФАНИ: ТАРАҚҚИЁТИ ВА ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ**АННОТАЦИЯ**

Ҳар қандай тараққиёт илмга асосланади. Фан тараққиётисиз жамият тараққиётини, жамият фаровонлигини тасаввур этиб бўлмайди. Хусусан, фан глобал экологик таҳдидлар ва глобал муаммоларга ечим топади. Ўзбекистонда экология фанининг ривожланиши, ибтидоси, эволюцияси ўзига хос босқичларга эга. Бу умуммиллий тараққиётнинг муҳим қисмига айланди. Бу борадаги назарий қарашлар, амалий ҳаракатлар мазкур мақолада муҳокама қилинади.

Калит сўзлар: фан, популяция, биосфера, антропоэкология, демоэкология, экосистема, табиат, табиий ресурс, фитоэкология, биоценоз, ландшафт.

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ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ НАУКА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: РАЗВИТИЕ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Любой прогресс основан на науке. Без развития науки невозможно представить развитие общества, благополучие общества. В частности, наука находит решение глобальных экологических угроз, общемировых проблем. Развитие, Генезис, эволюция экологической науки в Узбекистане имеет свои этапы. Он стал важной частью общенационального развития. Об этом и пойдет речь в статье.

Ключевые слова: Наука, популяция, биосфера, антропоэкология, демоэкология, экосистема, природа, природный ресурс, фитоэкология, биоценоз, ландшафт.

INTRODUCTION AND RELEVANCE.

Modern conditions dictate the need for scientific organization of the implementation of the state environmental policy. To do this, it becomes an urgent need to develop environmental science that studies environmental problems in all levels of additional education, in research institutes. Ecology – the relationship of living organisms, their connection with the external environment in which they live and live is a science that teaches various connections in the systems of organisms. Along with the fact that environmental science is an integral part of biological science, it includes chemistry, physics, geology, forestry, agriculture, with soil science, mathematics and other natural sciences are closely related.

The German scientist E. Geckon was the first to introduce the term “ecology” into science. This term refers to the environment in which the living world surrounds itself and teaches their relationship with the environment. By definition, Ch. Darwin, “creates conditions for the struggle for survival”.

The subject of ecological science is living organisms, populations, species, organization at the biotic and biospheric levels, it is an ecosystem and its interaction with the surrounding world.

The main object of studying ecology is the ecosystem, or the natural unity of complexes, the formation of living organisms and this is the environment in which they live.

The main task of ecology is new views on nature, society and their interrelation, the study of human society as part of the biosphere. The task of ecology is diverse and consists in providing developments based on the general laws of ecological systems, studying biodiversity and developing a mechanism for its conservation, assessing and anticipating the danger expected as a result of human impact, preserving, multiplying and rationally using natural resources.

RESEARCH METHODS.

The development of environmental science has been going on in stages since the 60s of the XIX century. Initially, ecology was considered a branch of biological science. By the beginning of the XX century, the theoretical conclusions of a number of major scientists, including such as Adams and A.Tapsly, Ch.Elpeon, V.N.Sukachev and V.I.Vernadsky, A.Humboldt, Ch.Darwin, V.V.Dokuchaev, G.F. Morozov and others, thanks to the discoveries on the study of nature and living organisms, the foundation of ecological science was laid in it [1].

In Uzbekistan, a number of scientists have also contributed to the development of environmental science. Among them, scientists such as S.Z.Zokirov, A.M.Muzaffarov, D.N.Kashkarov, N.I.Granitov, T.Rakhimova, A.E. Ergashev and others developed specific aspects of environmental science in their works. They seriously contributed to his obtaining the status of science. In 1919, the first university in Central Asia appeared - Turkestan State University was opened. In 1923, this university became a secondary one and was renamed the Asian State University. Since these years, it was here that scientists of the former Soviet Union began their activities and made a great contribution to the development of Central Asian environmental science.

The scientific founders of the science of ecology of Central Asia were D.N.Kashkarov and E.P.Korovins, who came to Uzbekistan during the creation of the Central Asian State University and conducted large-scale research work. D.N.Kashkarov, together with V.N.Sukachev, developed thoughts about biocenosis. Study of ecology with geography - mountainous, foothill, hilly, desert terrain of Uzbekistan studied plants, the landscape of their location.

RESEARCH RESULTS.

These scientists, together with the medical staff, conducted research work, developing methods that can be used to preserve human health and treat certain diseases. A scientist who worked on animal ecology, A. Pavlovsky's merits in this are also great.

The scientist scientifically theoretically and practically substantiated the laws of the development of animals, plants and humans in their interrelation. D.N.Kashkarov's books "Environment and Community", "Synecology" still serve the formation and development of environmental science. These books were published in 1933 in translated into English by Ch .Adams. American and English scientists Ch.Elton, R. Chapman and others having read the books of D.N.Kashkarov, they made serious discoveries in the science of ecology.

Also, D.N.Kashkarov and E.P. Korovin were the first to write a monograph of the "Ecology of the Desert". In this work, written on the basis of materials and scientific foundations collected after a number of expeditions, the authors provided comprehensive information about desert plants, their biology, and distribution area. The work, which provided relevant information at that time, was quickly translated into French [2].

E.P.Korovin, a major phytoecologist who conducted expeditions and discovered the truth, is a specialist visited the Phytoecology of Central Asia and reviewed. Scientist distribution of Central Asian plants. He had drawn his own map depending on the zones. He researched the biocenosis of the development of the flora of the land and deserts, scientifically substantiated it. These two scientists have substantiated the geography, landscapes, deserts, mountainous regions of Central Asia, the evolution and hydrolimate of the Karakum Desert. N. Babushkin also belongs to the number of scientists of this school.

Central Asia thanks to the research of these scientists, it became the ecology of high-altitude areas and deserts of the former SSSR, it remained a laboratory for study. R.I. Abolin in 1920 described the landscapes of Central Asia for the first time in many years and drew a soil-biological map of its territory.

A contemporary of academician R.U. Rakhimbekov, one of the promising students of the Kashkar school, he conducted large-scale scientific research in the field of studying the biology of the desert and mountainous regions of Central Asia for the development of the science of ecology and geography. He made great discoveries in this area. The first to introduce the term "Biosphere" was J.B. Lamarck (1744-1829), who introduced into science his manifesto "the place and the earth on which life extends the influence of living organisms on the processes of vital activity occurring on the surface". After Lamarck E. Suess in 1875 (Austria) introducing the term "biosphere" into science for the second time, he defined it describes and characterizes it as "a special shell scattered over the earth". This is how ideas about the ecology (populations) of plants, animals, and species were formed.

In the 1430s, based on the scientific works of the English scientist Ch.Elton's population ecology emerged. This is when a scientist proposed to study the population as a unit when studying individual individuals. Another branch of ecology is experimental ecology.

In the 30s of the century, the name of G.F. Gause is associated with the fact that he "ecology of experiment", conducting experiments on slippers he founded his science. In 1935, the English scientist A. Tepsley introduced the concept of "ecosystem", and this word quickly found its place.

Russian scientist V. N. Sukachev in 1942 scientifically recognized the concept of "biogeocenosis". He came to the conclusion that organisms interact in their habitat with abiotic factors, that all organisms and the inorganic environment are connected to each other, that the circulation of substances in nature and the formation of energy is the basis of biogeocenosis.

Consequently, the development of ecosystem which investigated by Vernadsky, which made it possible to prove the supply of the biosphere on ecological grounds. The scientist believes that the biosphere has formed as a global ecosystem. It obeys the laws of the environment, maintains the balance of matter and energy in one state.

In 1964, the International Biological Program was adopted. The program based on the maximum biological efficiency of our home planet and the demographic situation, the demand for the use of scientists from all over the world has been investigated.

The science of ecology gradually grew and was enriched with new scientific concepts based on research that scientists conducted consistently and effectively. The ecosystem, biocenosis and biosphere were formed as a science as a result of fundamental research by scientists. Back in those days, humanity considered itself the master of nature, and “we must learn to control nature.” At the end of the XIX and the beginning of the XX century, that is, in the era of ecology. Great scientists such as J.B. Lamarck and T. Malthus warned mankind about the dangers arising from exposure to nature. But this state has become a victim of the fundamental policy and interests of humanity.

Darwin scientifically proved the basic laws of evolutionary development in the organic world. “The struggle for survival”, justified the interrelation and interdependence of living organisms in the abiotic environment with his theoretical and practical conclusions.

The process of evolution is not controlled by anyone, and an invisible coincidence is the result of mutation and natural selection. Modern evolution is built and developed on the basis of reliable scientific knowledge.

There are more than forty modern branches of environmental science. In the future, this figure will only increase. So far, ecology can be divided into three main areas. Produces:

- General ecology-the study of the habitat of living organisms and their relationships.
- Theoretical ecology-studies and identifies general patterns in the organization of life processes.
- Applied ecology-studies the mechanism of causing harm to the biosphere of mankind, develops methods for preventing these processes and develops principles of environmental protection and rational use of natural resources.

General ecology, in turn, is divided into: special or autecology, population ecology or demoeology, category ecology or synecology.

Ecology is divided into historical and evolutionary ecology, obeying the flow of time. Also at this time, the ecology of plants, the Ecology of animals, the ecology of microorganisms were formed. Today, based on the consequences of natural development, a global science of ecology has emerged, and this science is ecological on Earth, studying problems and the biosphere as a global ecosystem.

In the formation of people's attitude to nature there is another special science – Social ecology (Social Ecology).

This science is developed by the interrelation of human society and nature. Another separate and extremely important field is Human Ecology (anthropoecology), which studies the interaction of a person as a biosocial living being with the surrounding world. Already, because of selfishness, greed, immorality and moral decay, nature is being greatly damaged. The environment deteriorates thanks to man, who is an integral and integral part of nature. Thus, human ecology - anthropoecology- has become the most important part of science.

The ecology of modernity, political, legal bodies, economics, is closely related to psychology, pedagogy and spirituality, human interaction with the external environment and related problems are constantly being studied. Its mission in society is economic, social, spiritual directions of development and individual indicators of scientific and technological achievements aimed at eliminating negative consequences between a person and the external environment. The term Ecology today gradually reaches the consciousness of every person, forcing them to think about the environment in which they live. Ecological views serve the realization of biocentric principles between human society and nature. Ecology is considered the theoretical basis of rational nature management and environmental protection [3].

Modern environmental science is a set of sciences that study complex problems of interaction between humans and the environment. As a result of the urgency and complexity of these problems, many natural, technical and humanitarian sciences were ecologized, as a result of which ecology was divided into branches and a number of directions were formed. These are geocology, agricultural ecology, engineering ecology, space ecology, mathematical ecology, etc. So, civilization, universal human progress also covers the science of ecology. He is discovering his new directions. Global environmental degradation, fierce competition between man and nature dictate this.

Today, for humanity, the introduction of ecology, ecological consciousness and understanding into everyday life is gaining important social significance. The role of environmental education and upbringing in the formation of ecological consciousness is great, it is necessary to rebuild the thinking of citizens through environmental education in people, change the way of life and spirituality of people. Until now, the ideas of disobedience to environmental laws, a selfish view of nature are embedded in the minds of people. As a result of people's indifference to nature, problems such as global warming and climate change, desertification, and the drying up of the Aral Sea lead to irreparable environmental crises [4].

The formation of an ecological concept exclusively by man and exclusively by man is an anthropocentric concept.

The features of the concept of anthropocentrism are confirmed in the following cases:

- formation of a person's idea that nature is the most valuable source of life and happiness, and nature is an integral part of a person;
- the concept of the world is hierarchically represented in the form of a pyramid, in which a person stands at the top or at the top, while all other benefits are below him (from person to person), and the lowest are various types of nature objects;
- all human requirements are met naturally, without abuse of nature;
- the predominance of the fact that interaction with nature is the most correct solution for man and humanity;
- moral laws and rules between people on earth, only for people they are a spiritual and normative rule in connection with man and nature;
- the further development of nature should be considered as a process in which a person in the process of his development does not obey, but is in connection with it.

In fact, ideas about development are changing.

Man and nature are one. They cannot be distinguished from each other, therefore it is wrong to oppose man and nature to each other is considered meaningless. One thing should be remembered- a person cannot live without nature, and nature can exist without a person.

Man is able to change or lose the laws of nature the laws of nature continue to evolve even without human order or will. Man can never be the master of nature. Man is inherent in nature and lives in it. Man cannot change the laws of nature. Perhaps the correct use of the laws of nature determines the intellectual capabilities and moral level of humanity.

Environmental education-based on a targeted plan, the development of systemic environmental knowledge, culture, qualifications and education in the learning process. Currently, the system of environmental education is formed on the basis of a continuous, cumulative, interdisciplinary specialty of an integrated nature. Centers of ecological education of the population are being created, the general public is expanding its knowledge in the field of ecology.

Environmental upbringing - consolidation of knowledge about nature conservation, nature conservation and environmental readings is carried out first at school, and then in higher educational institutions. As people get younger, their ideas about the environment expand, they look at nature with different eyes and gradually realize that it is their duty to love nature and protect it. The main task of environmental education at present is:

- all life processes are extremely important, valuable and unique, a person is responsible for wildlife;
- nature is eternal and inexhaustible, therefore it comes from man a strong person must interact with nature, constantly adapt to it and help it when necessary, to be against nature is resistance to oneself;
- the more diverse the biosphere, the more stable it is;
- man causes immeasurable harm to the environment;
- nature is huge against the harm it does to humanity can blow with force;
- the anthropological damage must be replaced concepts carried out in the ecocenter;
- people can change their worldview and behavior as a result of excessive consumption and scarcity, which leads to harm, since in one case or another environmental responsibility weakens. It

is necessary to intensify environmental education and upbringing, to carry out large-scale research work. At the biological faculties of universities, it is necessary to increase the scale of scientific work on restoring and maintaining ecological balance, cleaning the atmosphere from industrial and agricultural waste, maintaining soil and water purity, efficient use of forests and pastures, and studying their reproduction. Creating a healthy life must necessarily be a sacred work not only of specialists, but also of all people. Environmental education and upbringing should not only be one-sided, but also reflected in general education. An emerging person should receive environmental knowledge first at home, and then at school, college and institute [5].

CONCLUSION.

The formation of ecological culture is the formation of ecological consciousness and understanding that a person is in close connection with the environment. The main idea of ecological culture is that the connection between man and nature should not be material, but spiritual. Every person should be obliged not to harm nature and to think globally. In order for eternal life to exist on Earth, humanity needs to constantly protect the land on which it lives, rejuvenate it anew and develop ecological culture.

The renewing Uzbekistan is going through a large-scale creative process. It is a political, spiritual and spiritual phenomenon associated with both global and territorial ecological consciousness. Within the framework of the global problems raised by the President of Uzbekistan at international stands, an important place is occupied by measures to preserve the environment, harmonize the relations of nature and man in Central Asia and, in particular, in Uzbekistan, to overcome environmental degradation.

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ISSN 2181-0796

Doi Journal 10.26739/2181-0796

KONSENSUS XALQARO JURNALI

4 JILD, 1 SON

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONSENSUS

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1

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